

MEDICINAL PROPERTIES OF PLANTAGO MAJOR L

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Annotation: This article provides information on the appearance and geographical distribution of the plant (*Plantago major* L.), its uses, chemical composition and uses, and its specific medicinal properties.

Key words: Essential oil, mucous substances, saponins, auxin glycoside, vitamin C, carotene, flavonoid, organic acids, bitter, astringent and other substances, saponins, tincture, decoction.

Plantaginaceae herb with a short and thick rhizome belonging to the Plantaginaceae family. In the upper part of the earth, the leaves on the rhizome and the flower axis 10-15 cm high make up. The leaves are long, winged, broadly ovate or broadly elliptic, with 3-9 arcuate main veins with raised edges. The flower axis has one or more small, inconspicuous, four-lobed flowers located in a spike-like inflorescence inside the flower axis. The fruit is an egg-shaped capsule with many seeds. It blooms and fruits in June and September. [1] (Picture1).

1- Picture1. (*Plantago major* L.)

The above-ground part is collected when the plant is in bloom and sent to pharmaceutical factories to extract sap from it without drying. The leaves and tops contain 0.1% essential oil, mucilage saponins, aucubin glycoside, vitamin C (up to 300 mg %) and K 4.5-32.91 mg % carotene, flavonoids (luteolin, scutellarsin, aligenin, baikalalis and their glycoside. T-factor, organic acids, bitter, astringent and other substances in the seeds contain up to 22% fatty saponins, up to 44% mucilage and other substances. [2]

Plantaginaceae is a plant that has been used for the treatment of various diseases in folk medicine since ancient times. Abu Ali Ibn Sina used its leaves to treat hard-to-heal wounds, tumors (including dangerous tumors), eye inflammation, liver, kidney and other diseases and to

stop bleeding. In case of liver and kidney diseases and spitting blood, the patient was given a decoction of the seeds of zubtutum, and the juice of the undried leaves or seeds was injected into the intestinal ulcer. Leaf tincture or undried leaf juice is used in folk medicine to treat respiratory tract, eye, skin, malaria, gonorrhoea, colon inflammation, and various infectious diseases, as well as wounds, anthrax, and various bleeding disorders. used in stopping. Plantaginaceae is leaf is also used to treat lung and stomach cancer and as an expectorant in respiratory diseases. Freshly plucked leaves are crushed and bandaged to treat wounds, scabs, and cuts. [3]

A freshly collected leaf of Plantaginaceae is crushed, mixed with an equal amount of sugar and stored in a warm place for 3 weeks. After that, 3-4 teaspoons of juice separated from this mixture is given to the patient to treat lung and stomach cancer.

In conclusion, it can be said that the distribution of the large zubtutum plant, its appearance and medicinal properties were covered in this article. The big zubtutum plant is a cure for many diseases. It is especially used in the treatment of eye inflammation, liver, kidney and other diseases.

Drug preparation and use

1. To make a tincture, add 1 tablespoon of crushed zubtutum leaves to 1 cup of boiling water in a lidded container and infuse for 2 hours. Then float on gauze and drink 1 tablespoon 4 times a day 20 minutes before meals to treat the above diseases.

2. Tab lespoons of freshly cut and ground leaves are put in a bowl and mixed with sugar or honey, covered and kept in a warm place until the juice is released. In order to treat various diseases, juice is drunk 1 teaspoon half an hour before meals 4 times a day.

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